

IMPROVEMENT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF SOCIALIZATION
OF PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: The article discusses the psychological socialization of preschool children and the necessary recommendations for them. The psychology of preschool children and their socialization factors and problems have been studied and analyzed, and information on ways to overcome them has been provided.

Keywords: personality, psychology, preschool age, environment, family, neighborhood, interpersonal relationship, motivation, education

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Introduction: A child is the essence of human life, the continuation of the lineage, and the strong chain of the family. An intelligent, knowledgeable, hardworking child is the greatest asset not only of parents but of the entire society. Usually, a child grows up both physically and mentally in a family. Family harmony plays an important role during their growing up. Especially, it represents their service to the society with their spiritual education. It is the responsibility of parents to raise our children to be healthy, religious and physically strong. The Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, said, "Teach your children to swim in water, shoot a bow, throw a spear, and ride a horse!" He encouraged his ummah to raise their children to be agile, healthy, strong, and intelligent (narrations of Tirmidhi and Abu David). Because a healthy psychologically mature child brings benefits to his country everywhere. Based on the above points, we can understand that everything depends on the child's psychology. Child psychology, especially preschool child psychology, is very important. is complicated. Therefore, based on my knowledge and skills, I think it is appropriate to focus more on preschool children. Because at this age, that is, preschool age 3-4, 5-6- 7 at this age, the child thinks very quickly and his psychology is very complex and his interests are diverse. In addition, the developing child's psychology goes back to the family, because the child mainly distinguishes 2 different environments, i.e. the family and the place where he goes, i.e. kindergarten is definitely a different environment in the kindergarten, and a special environment in the family. therefore, the environment in the family can have a great impact on the kindergarten, that is, on the place of education and on

the psychology of the children there. This place of education, i.e. kindergarten, can affect the family. Therefore, we should pay attention to our child at the preschool age.

The main part: Summing up from all the information and opinions we have given, we should not create 2 different opinions and views in the child, that is, the family is positive and the kindergarten is negative, or it can be the other way around. Therefore, it is necessary and necessary for our parents and us to work together with qualified pedagogues. Only then will we achieve the great results we envision. And we will grow up to be mature and perfect children for the development of our country. We were drawn to such an aspect of the psychology of children of preschool age that, in this period, they, together with their interests and activities in plot-role-playing games, which are their leading activities, focus on the roles of the social world, first of all, on the roles of the parents and the family. they pay attention to mutual relations and begin to master the behaviors specific to parenthood.

The child becomes an observer and participant of the events happening in front of him, and the more dynamic these processes are, the more active and curious he is, the more, fuller and receives, assimilates and thinks about various information. In this case, the family becomes an important society - a social environment that forms the child's self, and it is important to realize that he is related to this environment. It should be noted here that, according to social psychologists, in the structure of interpersonal relations in the family, father-mother-child relations are relatively late in evolution and more specific in terms of content, because they arise during the already formed couple's relations.

We are convinced that the couple's relationship in a married couple is flexible and dynamic compared to the parental relationship indirectly expressed in the child's social imagination, and therefore the child's reflection of the parent's relationship becomes the basis for the changes expressed in his personality. For example, in mothers and fathers, the total degree of agreement of parental attitudes is from 0 to 5, while the degree of incompatibility of general indicators in the hierarchy of family values is from 1 to 11, that is, the same degree of parental relations was 2 times larger compared to the indicator. The primary self-attitude formed under the influence of internal relations in the family and the attitude of parents to the child is a decisive factor in the development of the child's self-awareness in the family as a primary small social group in all forms of self-identification and as a subject of communicative activity. is considered In this case, not only the relationship between the couple-parents and their relationship to the child, but also the fact that these relationships are directly reflected in the communication with him is of great importance.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said at the event dedicated to the problems of preschool educational institutions: "According to the scientific conclusions of experts and pedagogues, 70% of all the information and knowledge that a person receives during his life is received before the age of 5. . This fact alone clearly shows how important kindergarten education is for our children to grow up as mature and well-rounded individuals. There is no need to go far in search of additional proof of this. "If you compare a child who received kindergarten education with a child who did not go to kindergarten, it is not difficult to notice that there is a huge difference between their level of thinking." In the psychology of children of preschool age, taking into account that qualitative changes in children of this age have accelerated, it is considered appropriate to study this period by dividing it into three stages: junior preschool period (3-4 years old); pre-secondary school period (4-5 years old); senior preschool age (up to 5-6 years old); school enrollment age (6-7 years old).

In the course of development, a preschool child enters into a special relationship with the objects and events created by his ancestors, the mysteries of the universe. He actively assimilates and takes possession of the achievements made by mankind. A child's understanding of the world of objects and phenomena, actions performed with their help, mother tongue and relationships between people, development of activity motives, growth of abilities at the same time takes place on the basis of the direct help of adults.

CONCLUSION: It can be said that the family is entrusted with a huge and necessary social mission. It is clear that raising a child is the most difficult social task. A personal and positive example of a father and mother is a guarantee for the development of righteous and righteous children. When the child crosses the threshold and steps into the outside world, the influence of the environment and society on the child becomes significant. Educational institutions and the environment of the neighborhood, in general, the social sphere, haunt the human child until the last moment of his life. Therefore, achieving the formation of a person's universal worldview in family relations is important not only in personal life, but also in the social and economic changes taking place in our country and their development in the spiritual and spiritual improvement of the society.

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